

ISic0978

I.Sicily inscription 0978

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2018.01.19 (Manenti)

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag made minor edits

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of Santa Maria di Gesù

Coordinates

37.076291, 15.289549

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 294

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 10 cm

Width 18 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ούρσάνους
2. Αύγουστάλις
3. λανκιάρις □

Apparatus

Text based upon photograph (staurogram omitted in published editions)

Translation

Commentary

Oursanos may be the name Ursianus. The military unit 'Lanciarum Augustensium' is attested among the units serving under military magistrates for Illyricum in the Notitia Dignitatum, in partibus Orientis IX.36 (ed. Seeck p.29). If that list pertains to the beginning of the fifth century, that suggests the approximate period for an attestation of such a unit. Manganaro contextualises the inscription (with text of IG) in relation to others pertaining to military figures in the C4-6 AD in eastern Sicily.

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Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*. Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 580

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Photograph Museo Arch. Reg. P. Orsi: Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014